

31-10-2024

Deliverable D4.5

Exploitation and Sustainability - Interim report

Contractual Date:	31-10-2024
Actual Date:	31-10-2024
Grant Agreement No.:	101095055
Work Package:	WP4
Task Item:	Task 4.4
Nature of Deliverable:	R (Report)
Dissemination Level:	PU (Public)
Lead Partner:	EFIS Centre
Authors:	Matias Barberis (EFIS Centre); Carmela Asero (EFIS Centre)

Abstract

This deliverable will outline an initial set of ideas on sustainability and exploitation of project's results. This interim report includes an analysis of pathways to impact emerging from the project activities and how the consortium is preparing actions for sustainability regarding key concepts such as governance, funding schemes, infrastructure maintenance, data management and uptake as well as legal and security issues. This analysis will set out the foundations for the discussions on exploitation.

Funded by
the European Union

© European Future Innovation System Centre on behalf of the SUBMERSE project. The research leading to these results has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101095055 (SUBMERSE).

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Document Revision History

[This section to be deleted or hidden before publication of deliverable]

Version	Date	Description of change	Person
0.1	19-08-24	Structure and content outline	M. Barberis
0.2	30-08-24	First draft	M. Barberis
0.3	12-09-24	Introducing workshop results – from all partners	M. Barberis
0.4	20-09-24	Description of project expected results	C. Atherton – F. Tilmann – E. Parisi
0.5	03-10-24	Definition of impact pathways and overall review of the deliverable	M. Barberis – C. Asero
0.6	28-10-24	Review and comment from partners	R. Kvatadze; C. Atherton; E. Griniece; F. Tilmann
0.7	30-10-24	Final draft	M. Barberis – C. Asero
1.0	31-10-24	Submission	M. Barberis

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	1
1 Introduction	2
1.1 About the project	2
2 Methodological approach	3
3 Analysis of project pathways to impact	4
4 Project sustainability	9
4.1 Initial consortium discussion	9
4.2 Co-creation workshop	12
5 Initial roadmapping of exploitation actions	16
6 Next steps	18

Table of Figures

Figure 1. Sustainability and exploitation methodological design	3
Figure 2. Overview of SUBMERSE activity-results-outcome-impact logics	5
Figure 3. Sustainability and Exploitation Internal Workshop in Potsdam, Germany	13
Figure 4. Initial design of roadmap for exploitation	16

Table of Tables

Table 1. Overview of online consultation key results	9
Table 2. Co-creation workshop agenda	12
Table 3. Preliminary list of actions and barriers for exploitation	17

Executive Summary

This report provides an interim analysis of sustainability and exploitation pathways for the SUBMERSE project, that focuses on developing a standardised scientific instrument that utilises active submarine fibre-optic communication cables for data collection. The project's ultimate goal is to enhance ocean, geohazard and environmental monitoring by integrating Distributed Acoustic Sensor (DAS) and State of Polarisation (SOP) systems. These technologies are deployed across multiple locations, providing large-scale, open datasets useful for scientific, industrial, and public sectors.

Key findings include the project's significant potential to contribute to scientific advancement, environmental sustainability, and industrial competitiveness by leveraging existing fibre-optic infrastructure. SUBMERSE is not only pioneering new data handling methodologies but is also fostering interdisciplinary collaboration between academia, industry, and public organisations. This contributes to position SUBMERSE as a potential leader in advancing fibre-sensing technologies relevant to marine and environmental monitoring.

The **project's impact** spans several domains. Scientifically, it contributes to new discoveries by deploying and configuring new research tools towards a standardised processing promoting interdisciplinary collaboration. In societal terms, SUBMERSE fosters knowledge exchange and raises awareness on environmental issues such as climate change and develops applications of the new infrastructure in seismology, oceanography and marine research. Economically, the project's collaboration with industry drives innovation and enhances Europe's competitiveness in environmental monitoring. Environmentally, SUBMERSE will provide critical insights into ecosystem dynamics, contributing to sustainable marine and land management.

Key **sustainability challenges** include the need for a clear governance structure to manage the infrastructure and the generated data. The project looks to fusion with existing networks to benefit from established dissemination mechanisms and governance structures, thus avoiding redundancy. As technologies evolve rapidly, maintaining and upgrading the submarine cables and monitoring instruments will require sustained partnerships and funding streams. Effective data management is also crucial, balancing long-term storage with the need to comply with security and legal requirements while adhering to FAIR data principles.

The initial outline of the **exploitation strategy** is organised in key issues prioritised by actions and barriers in the short, medium and long-term. The exploitation vision is aligned with the sustainability strategy, while ensuring the achievement of the high-level pathways to impacts. Looking ahead, the project will focus on refining exploitation actions and finetuning a roadmap for sustainability, based on the learnings from implementation and the collective vision of the project partners.

1 Introduction

This report is the **interim version of the sustainability and exploitation** analysis of SUBMERSE project. This report presents preliminary findings of task 4.4 that explores the long-term sustainability of the technology developed and used in the project, the sustainable use of fibre-optic cables to perform the research and investigate societal applications such as environmental monitoring and early warning for natural disasters, ensuring the longevity of the data products produced for the research community.

This interim report will present preliminary findings of an impact analysis that serves as foundation for the consortium discussions on sustainability and exploitation. This document responds to the question of how to make the pathways to impact sustainable and design exploitation strategies for key project outputs, accelerating the achievement of desired impacts. It will also present the outcomes of online and in-person discussions on key sustainability and exploitation areas such as governance and funding models, infrastructure maintenance and data management and uptake. It also outlines initial ideas on security and legal aspects, IP management and ownership, topics that will be further developed during the second phase of the project.

1.1 About the project

The SUBMERSE project is a response to the call Next generation of scientific instrumentation, tools, and methods (HORIZON-INFRA-2022-TECH-01). It aims to improve scientific research by developing an advanced instrument that leverages existing ocean submarine fibre-optic communication cables. Integrating advanced sensing equipment on active cables operated by the National Research and Education Networks (NREN) will enrich the data services offered by organisations like the European Plate Observing System (EPOS-ERIC) and the Copernicus Marine Service by enabling the collection and dissemination of FAIR-compliant Distributed Acoustic Sensor (DAS) and State of Polarisation (SOP) data.

At the heart of SUBMERSE is the development of a standardised scientific instrument that integrates both DAS and SOP technologies into a single telecommunications submarine cable system. This system is being deployed in at least three geographically diverse locations – Norway, Greece, and Portugal – also in collaboration with Pan-European and Pan-American institutions, offering long-term, consistent ocean bottom and near-shore monitoring capabilities. The project also focuses on producing large-scale, open datasets by designing an efficient data processing workflow. These datasets, made machine-readable and accessible, will benefit a broad range of users, including scientific, industrial, and public sectors.

Furthermore, SUBMERSE will assess the cost-efficiency of using existing telecommunication systems, thus contributing to the technological advancement of the global telecom industry and creating new market opportunities. The project will also emphasise training and capacity-building activities, enhancing the ability of stakeholders to collect, interpret, and reuse the data generated. By developing a roadmap and strategy for sustainable research infrastructure, SUBMERSE aims to ensure the long-term viability of both the infrastructure and the data it generates, thereby strengthening the European research area and its integration into global innovation systems.

2 Methodological approach

The analysis of sustainability and impact is based on a methodological design that looks to capture different perspectives from consortium partners and a wider network of stakeholders. The first phase of this task involved collection of information through an online consultation and meetings with key stakeholders at relevant conferences, and directly in a dedicated workshop. This information was analysed using content analysis and validated with the consortium, creating a collaborative mechanism of discussion and feedback to build solid basis for long-term sustainability.

In particular, the analysis follows a series of steps (see Figure below) that go from understanding the challenges and opportunities arising from the project implementation and analysing how project results lead to concrete impacts.

Figure 1. Sustainability and exploitation methodological design

We start by **analysing project impacts**, looking to identify how different project activities are paving the way to concrete impacts in four areas: scientific, societal, economic and environmental. This is done using the Theory of Change (ToC) approach¹, defined as a logical description of how and why anticipated changes take place. We look for causal links that help to reconstruct mechanisms on how SUBMERSE activities and data collected using the infrastructure generates some direct results (i.e., outputs) that can lead to certain short- or long-term effects (i.e. outcomes) and interacting with wider circumstances and influences lead to specific impacts. The report also outlines how the project pathways intersect with the nine pathways to impact proposed by the European Commission for assessing the Horizon Europe programme.

In the second phase, we **analyse sustainability** by mapping opportunities emerging from the implementation to maximise the (actual or expected) impacts, as well as barriers and challenges that could interfere with achieving outcomes and impacts in the long-term. This phase is structured around an online consultation and a co-creation workshop with project partners. For the consultation, a set of questions were prepared by the consortium, with the advice of the Advisory Board. The task leader, EFIS Centre, prepared a questionnaire via Microsoft Forms and sent it out for consultation to project partners, who provided different perspectives to aspects directly related to sustainability and exploitation (see section below). Following the analysis of these results, four key topics were identified -governance, funding mechanisms, infrastructure maintenance and data management- and discussed in-depth at the face-to-face meeting of the consortium in September 2024.

The third phase of **planning for exploitation** will be the core focus in the second half of the project. We will analyse scenarios where the technology could be better exploited and discuss with different stakeholders how to achieve this. An outline of exploitation strategies emerging from the co-creation workshop are also outlined in this interim report.

3 Analysis of project pathways to impact

This section of the report will focus on understanding how all the different activities implemented in the project are contributing to the impact pathways outlined at the beginning of the project. In particular, this section will present an overall understanding of the pathways, including a definition and what it means in the medium and long-term. Furthermore, it will align the impact domains with the pathways of impact proposed by the Horizon Europe programme². The following figure, depicts the overview of how activities connect to results, expected outcomes and planned impacts.

¹ Funnell, S.C. & Rogers, P. J. (2011). Purposeful program theory: Effective use of theories of change and logic models. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass/Wiley.

² European Commission: Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Stančiauskas, V., Brozaitis, H., Notten, A., Hollanders, H. et al., Study to support the monitoring and evaluation of the framework programme for research and innovation along key impact pathways – Indicator methodology and metadata handbook, Stančiauskas, V.(editor), Brozaitis, H.(editor), Notten, A.(editor), Hollanders, H.(editor), Papageorgiou, H.(editor), Manola, N.(editor), Zagame, P.(editor) and Le-Mouel, P.(editor), Publications Office of the European Union, 2022, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/44653>

Figure 2. Overview of SUBMERSE activity-results-outcome-impact logics

- **SCIENTIFIC DOMAIN: Supporting innovation from basic and applied research through development of high-tech standardised research instruments.**

This pathway investigates how Research Infrastructures (RIs) **standardised technologies could unlock scientific advancement and innovation** in various fields. Within SUBMERSE project, the SOP and DAS systems are designed to enhance the precision, accuracy, and reliability of data collection and analysis across various research domains (seismology, oceanography, marine ecology, etc.). By standardising fibre-sensing instruments, SUBMERSE is catalysing innovation, thus sharing common approaches, methodologies and access, which ultimately means providing ground for competitive basic and applied research.

For instance, at the end of October 2023, a Distributed Acoustic Detection (DAS) interrogator was installed at the EMACOM Cable Landing Station in Praia Formosa, in Madeira Island, Portugal. The DAS technology makes it possible to transform communication cables into a chain of effectively hundreds of seismic sensors spaced a few metres apart. The position of the cable along the seabed also made it possible to not only record P and S waves from local earthquakes but also very clearly record acoustic signals that propagated through the water, the T waves, which are thought to be excited by coupling of elastic waves at significant seafloor topography. It is thus possible to not only determine the location of local earthquakes but understand the T wave excitation mechanisms by the first observations close to the excitation point. Apart from shedding light on the tectonically active structure and thus improving our knowledge of the earthquake hazard, a fast analysis of the signals from the cable might provide early warning for tsunamis, or in some localities, early warning of strong shaking. This example showcases not only the potential of this technology innovation in scientific terms – moving beyond the state of the art of collecting data for earthquakes and tsunamis but highlights a clear contribution of science to address societal challenges, here the danger from natural hazards, i.e. Tsunamis, earthquakes, and submarine volcanoes.

In the short term, the planned provision of standard analysis tools in SUBMERSE will enable researchers to quickly generate new observations from the data collected. This will enable researchers to produce comparable and consistent results, which helps advancing scientific knowledge. In the medium-term, these data collected through the submarine cables are expected to be widely adopted within the scientific community, contributing to the growth of a robust research infrastructure. This infrastructure will support the continuous development of new technologies and methodologies, driving innovation in both fundamental research and practical applications. In the long-term, the widespread use of these standardised tools will facilitate more complex and interdisciplinary research, leading to breakthroughs that address critical environmental and societal challenges, and ultimately, contributing to the long-term impact of sustainable marine and land management.

Connection to Horizon Europe Pathways to Impact

1. **Creating high-quality new knowledge:** Horizon Europe generates world-class science and creates and diffuses high-quality new knowledge. The implementation of standardised SOP (State of Polarisation) and DAS (Distributed Acoustic Sensing) systems will facilitate the generation of high-quality, consistent, and comparable research data across different domains.
2. **Strengthening human capital in Research and Innovation (R&I):** Horizon Europe strengthens human capital engaged in R&I. The project will enhance the skills and capabilities of researchers by providing access to advanced, standardised research tools and methodologies, as well as offering training in the effective use of these. This will improve their ability to conduct cutting-edge research, collaborate across disciplines, and achieve reliable results.
3. **Fostering the diffusion of knowledge and Open Science:** Open Science helps to develop a stronger system for science by giving Europe a competitive advantage through open knowledge. By enabling better and faster access to submarine data through fibre sensing techniques, SUBMERSE will enhance Europe’s competitive advantage in science and innovation.

- **SOCIETAL DOMAIN: Enhanced knowledge sharing between academia, industry and general public and awareness raising on socio-environmental issues.**

This pathway looks into the way **RIs can facilitate knowledge sharing** between key stakeholders such as research communities, industries and also broader public, leading to an **increased awareness of social and environmental issues**. By creating platforms and intersectoral networks (e.g. fibre sensing communities, etc.), the project promotes the exchange of ideas and research findings in various fields, also triggering different uptakes of research results. It also refers to the process of enhanced interdisciplinary and applied research in disciplines such as oceanography, biology, chemistry, or engineering.

An example of this pathway is the potential contribution of the data collected and curated through the fibre-sensing technology that could deliver critical real-time information on an ongoing earthquake rupture to national Tsunami warning systems. The infrastructure and new science built upon it address some of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs):

- SDG14 (Life Below Water) by providing seabed data with relevance to marine life, with relevance and effects to climate change and interestingly also of human activity close to the ocean floor.
- SDG9 (Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure) is supported by building the proof of concept for resilient detection systems based on submarine cable infrastructure.
- SDG13 (Climate Action) is supported by adding data sets to foster the protection, conservation and responsible use of our marine resources.

In the medium-term, this pathway is expected to result in a deeper understanding of socio-environmental issues across different sectors of society. In the long-term, this enhanced knowledge-sharing process could contribute to aligning societal, industrial, and academic efforts toward addressing societal challenges (e.g. earthquake and tsunami early detection and warning, etc.).

Connection with Horizon Europe Pathways to Impact

1. Delivering benefits and impact through R&I missions: pursuing clearly defined targets and delivering solutions to some of the greatest challenges facing our world. SUBMERSE addresses critical socio-environmental challenges by creating platforms for knowledge exchange and interdisciplinary collaboration in diverse fields (oceanography, seismology, etc.) connected to two key EU missions: Oceans and Waters and Climate Change.
2. Strengthening the uptake of research and innovation in society: it is expected that this will increase the relevance of science and innovation in society, while stimulating the societal uptake and deployment of innovative solutions and leveraging business investment.

- **ECONOMIC DOMAIN: Enhanced competitiveness of European industry through co-development with industrial actors of advanced technologies and tools.**

This pathway explores the **impact on European competitiveness** from joint development of technologies and tools with the private sector. This collaborative approach ensures that the generated innovations are not only cutting-edge but also market-ready, meeting the specific needs and demands for both applied research and industry. By integrating industry expertise and real-world application requirements into research and development process, SUBMERSE puts together industrial and scientific capabilities to create breakthrough innovation.

The core of the project innovation emerges from the collaboration of scientific and industrial partners to prototype, develop and install fibre-sensing technology. The EllaLink cable has opened up an opportunity to integrate a scientific component into a commercial submarine cable system. Including not only EllaLink but also CORIAN/Infinera and Alcatel Submarine cables next to a network of scientific partners and research

infrastructures in Europe is clear evidence of how these joint efforts could develop competitive technologies and tools. The example of initial set of data retrieved in Madeira is product of a shared development: the OptoDAS equipment, acquired by the Government of Madeira from Alcatel Submarine Networks, uses a fibre from the EllaLink cable to measure and record earthquake and marine data.

In the medium-term, the adoption of joint industry-academia developments will drive economic growth by opening new markets and enhancing the efficiency and sustainability of existing operations. The successful application of new technologies in different fields will reinforce the position of European companies as leaders in environmental technologies on the global stage. In the long-term, this pathway could contribute to the creation of a dynamic and innovative industrial ecosystem in Europe, capable of responding to emerging challenges and maintaining competitiveness in an evolving market landscape.

Connection with Horizon Europe Pathways to Impact

1. **Generating innovation-based growth:** to maintain and improve its relative competitiveness in the global economy, the EU needs a constant supply of new technological output and intellectual property. By integrating industry expertise into research and development process, SUBMERSE ensures that the technologies and tools developed are aligned with market needs and have strong commercial potential.
2. **Leveraging investments in R&I:** Horizon Europe is expected to play a role as a catalyst for R&D activities within industry, research and academia. SUBMERSE acts as a catalyst for further research, triggering not only quality research but also developing innovation in monitoring processes (e.g. disaster risk reduction).

- **ENVIRONMENTAL DOMAIN: Increased understanding of natural ecosystems leading towards resilient and sustainable marine and land environments.**

This pathway explores the potential of SUBMERSE technological developments to **improve the understanding of natural ecosystems**, that is key to addressing pressing environmental challenges. By conducting comprehensive and interdisciplinary research, the project aims to uncover the complex interactions and processes that govern ecosystem health and stability. The insights gained from applied research could serve as a foundation for informed decision-making aimed at preserving biodiversity and ecosystem services.

For instance, changes in the seabed can result from various factors, including ocean currents, marine organisms, and maritime activity. Some seabed changes are so subtle that they cannot be detected through conventional research methods. Technologies that employ in-line strain detection, like Distributed Acoustic Sensing (DAS), provide the capability to monitor even the tiniest shifts in the seabed. While this type of applications is still not processed within the research partners of the project, it is expected to increase research-related activities in this domain in the second half of the project, including also trainings in the environmental domain by LifeWatch ERIC.

In the medium-term, the body of knowledge generated will enable more precise and adaptive management of natural resources, ensuring that ecosystems can sustain their vital functions in the face of ongoing environmental changes. The project's findings will inform further multi-disciplinary understanding of our planet and its processes. In the long-term, these efforts will contribute to sustainability of marine and terrestrial environments, creating better ecological networks, capable of withstanding and recovering from disturbances, thus increasing resilience.

Connection with Horizon Europe Pathways to Impact

1. **Delivering benefits and impact through R&I missions:** pursuing clearly defined targets and delivering solutions to some of the greatest challenges facing our world. Through comprehensive research, the project provides valuable insights into natural ecosystem dynamics, which are essential for informed decision-making and effective management.

4 Project sustainability

The project sustainability is based on an online consultation and a co-creation workshop with project partners. For the online consultation, the WP leaders and the Advisory Board defined a series of guiding questions for the analysis, that constitute a starting point for broader discussions:

- What are the specific outcomes connected to project results (outputs)? How long do they take to materialise?
- What are the costs of ownership (including insurance) and legal obligations (including on security matters) to be assumed at the end of the project to ensure operational continuity?
- What affect sustainability of the equipment? How does depreciation and obsolescence affect operating these types of equipment and the related associated costs to be assumed? The EC supports depreciation, not full cost of ownership (which include insurance).
- Who is assuming responsibility of handling data collected in international waters and which entity is supposed to liaise with national authorities (cable owners?) on security aspects?
- What are key enablers and barriers for achieving the outcomes?
- What is the role of RIs and TIs in the pathways to impacts? Who are potential users of technology, who can trigger new pathways or reinforce the achievement of existing ones?
- Which actions are required to make these outcomes continue after project ends and are flexible to adapt for uncertain futures?
- What are potential areas of exploitation of project results in line with expected outcomes and impacts and aligning with key European strategic policy objectives?

4.1 Initial consortium discussion

The first consortium discussion on sustainability gathered insights from an online consultation (questionnaire using the questions above) that was carried out using Microsoft Forms. One third of partners replied to the questions, providing a varied discussion topics to bring to the attention of the whole consortium. The following table presents a summary of key aspects emerging from the consultation.

Table 1. Overview of online consultation key results

Topic	Main points of discussion
Project outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of infrastructure: the project aims to prototype a data infrastructure for distributing, accessing and storing DAS and SOP data, with significant outcomes like high-quality data generation applied to pilot demos. Also, key is to explore models for partnerships. • Applications: the high-quality data produced will be essential for various scientific fields, including geosciences, marine sciences, and climate studies, and will be valuable to organisations and companies involved in submarine cable systems and research networks.

Topic	Main points of discussion
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Broader engagement: there is a focus on expanding engagement with new user communities beyond traditional fields (e.g., seismology), and on positioning this project within larger research frameworks, such as inclusion in the ESFRI roadmap, to foster new scientific discoveries.
Enablers and barriers to achieve outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Key enablers: Success depends on effective communication, clear governance structures, securing long-term funding, and ensuring national organisations and stakeholders. Collaborative data sharing, national champions, and a well-defined security policy also play crucial roles. • Key barriers: Challenges include technological entry barriers, the cost of systems, and difficulties in maintaining engagement due to time delays. Additional barriers include issues with communication between national security agencies, lack of funding, insufficient scientific community uptake, and the need for better coordination between national entities, especially when cables span multiple countries.
Users and societal benefits	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Primary users and roles: Research centres, investigators, and national security agencies are key users who can trigger new pathways or reinforce the achievement of project impacts. The primary users include organisations in geosciences, marine sciences, and submarine cable service providers. • Pathways to impact: Societal benefits such as earthquake/tsunami early warning and oceanographic modelling are seen as crucial pathways to broader deployment and impact. The project's success relies on the long-term availability of data and its ability to be commercialised or used for public benefit. • Exploration of new users: There is a need to engage new users from various scientific disciplines and explore potential commercial applications, such as in cable protection, to maximise the impact of the project.
Operational continuity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Equipment and ownership: the equipment used in the project is typically lent for the duration, with post-project ownership and costs dependent on future negotiations, which have not yet been initiated. • Uncertain costs and legal obligations: unsure about the specific costs and legal obligations at the project's end, with assumptions that costs will fall within relevant infrastructures or specific national authorities. • Security and legal considerations: there may be legal obligations under the NIS2 directive as the network might be classified as critical infrastructure, necessitating the implementation of additional security measures.
Equipment sustainability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technology updates and depreciation: there is a need for regular updates to the hardware due to rapid technological advancements, with an expected replacement cycle of about five years. • Funding and storage challenges: sustainability may be affected by funding issues, particularly concerning the storage of large amounts of data. These storage costs and the quality of the data should be carefully considered. • Operational management: the suggestion is to establish a neutral third-party organisation at the national level to manage the equipment, ensuring equal access to the data for all scientists and maintaining sustainability.
Data collection and international law	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Responsibility for data handling: the responsibility for handling data collected in international waters generally lies with the project's coordinating entity at national level, such as INESC TEC in Portugal or the cable owners in specific countries.

Topic	Main points of discussion
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coordination with national authorities: the task of liaising with national authorities on security aspects is expected to be managed by either nationally mandated organisations, such as NRENs, or the cable owners, depending on the country and the project structure. • Role of national security agencies: it is suggested that having a strong link with national security agencies is important for handling and releasing data securely (including limited type of data for certain groups), ensuring that there are clear agreements and procedures in place.
Sustainability actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sustaining collaborations: effective communication of the project’s setups and collaborations is crucial for serving as a model for future initiatives and ensuring continued outcomes. • Securing financing: long-term financing is necessary, with a focus on engaging and securing the interest of NREN management. Emphasising the dual-use nature of the data, such as its relevance to both research and critical infrastructure protection, is key to obtaining long-term funding. • Building strong communities: Developing a strong community of research institutions, submarine cable service providers, and NRENs is essential. Integrating the technologies into larger projects like GÉANT and conducting thorough funding landscape analyses are also important to adapt and continue the project outcomes beyond its initial phase.
Areas of exploitation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Alignment with European Policy on Infrastructure Security: the project results align with the EU’s focus on securing and maintaining critical infrastructure, such as submarine cable networks, in line with the recent EU recommendation on Secure and Resilient Submarine Cable Infrastructures (February 2024). • Integration with Research Infrastructures: there is significant potential for integrating project results with existing European research infrastructures and initiatives, including EPOS-ERIC, EOSC, and LifeWatch ERIC, which emphasise the importance of data monitoring and safety in alignment with European strategic goals. • Community engagement: the project faces challenges in ensuring long-term sustainability and continued utilisation of its research agenda. Key considerations include the willingness of partners to maintain the project’s momentum, the potential for establishing a formal institutional framework, and the need for community consensus on funding and organisational support, potentially through workshops or partnerships with existing institutions like GÉANT.

4.2 Co-creation workshop

The second stage for sustainability analysis was a co-creation workshop held during the project F2F meeting in Potsdam on 4th September. The workshop was organised with the following agenda.

Table 2. Co-creation workshop agenda

Time	Activity
15:00 – 15:15	Introduction Matias Barberis, EFIS Centre
15:15 – 16:00	Breakout groups <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Governance model: towards a community of practice 2. Funding scheme: ensuring new streams to support the infrastructure 3. Maintenance planning: monitoring the infrastructure 4. Data management: enhancing research quality with new technologies <i>One moderator/rapporteur per group</i>
16:00 – 16:30	<i>Coffee break</i>
16:30 – 17:00	Harvesting in plenary Moderated by Carmela Asero and Matias Barberis, EFIS Centre

After a presentation of the approach to the workshop and dynamics, the participants divided in four groups to discuss in more detail four emerging topics: **governance, funding, infrastructure maintenance and data management**. One moderator and rapporteur were selected in each sub-group. An initial set of questions were distributed to the groups to stimulate the discussion.

1. Governance model: towards a community of practice

- a. What governance models are most effective for managing the infrastructure and the generated data?
- b. How can a community of practice enhance the effectiveness of governance structures in managing the project's data infrastructure?
- c. What are the potential challenges of establishing a community of practice for this project, and how can they be mitigated? Is there any existing structure that could integrate SUBMERSE approach (integrating an existing community of practice, e.g. fibre sensing?)

2. Funding scheme: ensuring new streams to support the infrastructure

- a. What are the most promising sources of long-term funding for maintaining and expanding the project's infrastructure?
- b. What role can partnerships or strong governance model with private sector entities play in supporting the project's financial sustainability?
- c. How can the project effectively communicate its value proposition to potential funders to secure ongoing financial support?

3. Maintenance planning: monitoring the infrastructure

- a. What are the key challenges in monitoring the project's infrastructure, and how can they be addressed?
- b. How frequently should maintenance and updates be performed to ensure the infrastructure remains operational and effective?
- c. How can the project ensure that maintenance planning is flexible enough to accommodate rapid technological advancements?

4. Data management: enhancing research quality with new technologies

- a. What are the most effective strategies for managing and storing large volumes of data generated by the project?
- b. What strategies can be implemented to increase the adoption of the project's data among research communities?
- c. What mechanisms should be put in place to facilitate collaboration and data sharing between researchers using the project's data?

Figure 3. Sustainability and Exploitation Internal Workshop in Potsdam, Germany

The following boxes summarises the main aspects and key uptake questions for a follow up discussion:

Governance and funding schemes

- The definition of governance models is associated to two key levels: the data and the infrastructure itself and should be differentiated.
- The governance model will contribute to reinforce the position of SUBMERSE and leverage funding opportunities, beyond a potential Horizon type funding continuity.
- There is no need to create another community but to see how the future of governance could be integrated with existing structures and communities of experts/practice:
 - GÉANT, working group on fibre sensing, focusing on what is new and strengthening collaboration with stakeholders.

- EPOS-ERIC, either through a newly formed TCS (Thematic Core Service) such as Fibre Optic Monitoring, or through existing Seismology and Tsunami TCS. EMSO is another relevant ERIC for seafloor measurements.
- For future activities and projects there is a great opportunity to look towards meteorological observations and users' communities.
- An important issue is about the costs associated to structures of governance – what streams of funding could be explored and what could be recycled (e.g. memberships to existing structures that take over, etc.)
- There is a need to define a value proposition to attract funders: the monitoring and research potential of the submarine cables. In terms of private stakeholders: what is the benefit for them? Also, this should be thought in the opposite way, how the scientific community could access and exploit data gathered by private stakeholders?
- Some limitations for governance models definitions: permission to owners of cables and storage of data.
- Need to benchmark existing governance schemes of distributed RIs, but also explore the US models.

Follow up discussion:

- What are the specific challenges related to governance models for data and for infrastructure, and how can they be addressed differently or in an integrated way?
- What strategies could be put in place to strengthen collaboration with private players already working or potentially interested to work with fibre sensing technology?
- What lessons can be drawn from governance models of distributed Research Infrastructures (RIs), both in Europe and the US?

Maintenance planning

Infrastructure split in three parts as they have different needs:

- Cable infrastructure
 - Operations of the cables is difficult, ~200 issue/year globally, who covers operational costs and repairs. In case of active cable there is a need to secure budget for the usage of the facility (in rare case some cables can be accessible for science). A sustainable approach could be using decommissioned Telcom cables whereby an agreement between operators and governments to allow scientific usage for free following decommissioning of the cable by the operator (here the problem is the cost of repairs in case of problems but also power costs to the cable landing station). Also using alternative transmission bands on cables that allows usage of active Telcom cables without disrupting existing business models. This could be facilitated by teaming up at an early stage with NRENS, as we do here. Collaboration with regulators could assist in gaining the ability to also act very early in the process to deal with government cable landing permits (for example saving money by requiring a cable operator to make available a single fibre for research/monitoring).
 - Operation time of cable is ~25 years, afterwards still a decade for monitoring... the technology for monitoring and data flow is changing much faster and so an additional societal use could be made of abandoned / end of life cables.
- Instruments
 - All new monitoring technologies are rapidly changing. This is estimated to be about 3 times the speed of the cable design/technologies, so during a lifetime of a cable we may see 3 different sensing technologies rolling over. This is dependent on the market.
 - The DAS technology cannot easily adapt to very old cables whereas other technologies can (thus in terms of sustainability they may be treated differently)
 - Clocks technology is moving fast. This has a link to meteorology communities and opens new sensing opportunities as a by-product of that implementation.

Maintenance planning

- The lifetime of a technology can be 6/7 years. The components required for maintenance and repair are troublesome to find after a decade, making it difficult to keep maintaining the instruments.
- There is a need for funding to buy new instruments. This would necessitate a series of projects to support the roll out of further instrumentation unless national funding will finance this in the future (this is scientific task). Currently such equipment has a relatively high cost, although as the market develops and matures the costs could potentially come down.
- Also, investigating the offering model as a means of turning key solutions or derived data into a product or service, including selling such products as something to consider. However, commercialising this service or product would need careful consideration with, amongst other aspects, respect to taxation within and outside of the European Economic Area.
- Data infrastructures
 - The most resilient part of the national infrastructures which form part of the distributed research instrument are the data storage infrastructures, as the public community repositories are funded long term by the various institutions. This is different for the national storage of raw data which needs dedicated funding or limited buffering.
 - Time is needed to adapt to new technologies/observables with standard formats that can be served over the long-term. Looking at the current situation it may take 3-4 years to adapt to serve DAS/SOP/etc data via a homogeneous data format.
- The lifetime of the project is too short to accommodate the changes but can facilitate and trigger early adoption of new standards/technologies.

Follow up discussion:

- How can we plan for the future planning considering the 25-year operational life of submarine cables with the rapidly changing monitoring technologies that may evolve every 6-7 years? What are the long-term plans to manage this time disparity?
- What new funding mechanisms or partnerships (national or international) could be pursued to cover the continuous need for instrument upgrades and replacements? How can the costs of scientific equipment be minimised as technology becomes more accessible?

Data management

- Strategies for managing and storing data:
 - Aim is not to store but instead extract, add value and destroy data.
 - Have a good data management plan since the beginning
 - Store as long as possible (needed) but delete oldest raw data (IPB- 220 days per DAS)
 - Only keep scientific interesting data for longer periods. This would require an automated means of identifying such data.
 - Long term archiving of a sample of the raw data (for machine learning purposes)
 - Inform stakeholders about data sampling times (for example announcing sampling every Sunday for low frequency observations)
 - There is a need to improve the understanding of what needs to be kept and what should be deleted – then users decide what to extract.
- Data script (conservancy after SUBMERSE)
 - National operators are responsible for keeping the scripts going after the project finishes and communities pushing national operators to keep things going.
 - Models to have a minimum of maintenance and overhead
 - Cleaning process needs to be as sustainable as possible
 - There should be also a national interest to keep things running

Data management

- How to increase adoption?
 - Give data without gaps (either micro or macro), good quality and open data
 - Good operational practices (reliable)
 - Partner providing data which has multiple uses – higher sampling frequencies
 - Standards for interrogators (SOP + DAS): consensus on operating interrogators: sampling frequency, length, channel sparing, number of channels, usable channels.
 - Easier way to access and understand the important information in a raw file.
 - What other groups are interested in, but not yet involved= Use cases, demos, marketing.
 - Schematic of what types of information and frequencies could be observed: instrument dependency.
- Mechanisms to facilitate collaboration:
 - Scientific production and participation in event
 - Use of existing ESFRI infrastructure
 - Increased sharing of what groups are doing
 - Following FAIR principles
 - Distribute data through established mechanisms
 - Agree on JSON format for data interoperability.

Follow up discussion:

- What incentives can be offered to national operators and stakeholders to ensure the continuation of data scripts and management after the SUBMERSE project finishes? How can the scientific community play a role in sustaining these efforts?
- How can we ensure open and high-quality data access without gaps? What operational practices and standards (e.g., SOP + DAS) should be established to make raw data more usable and understandable across diverse user groups?

5 Initial roadmapping of exploitation actions

Based on the data analysed through the online consultation and the discussions from the F2F workshop with consortium members, we have identified different strategic lines for exploitation. They are organised based on a potential timing for achievement, as in the following graphics.

Figure 4. Initial design of roadmap for exploitation

The following table presents in concrete the different actions to achieve the proposed targets and potential barriers for implementation.

Table 3. Preliminary list of actions and barriers for exploitation

Target timing	Actions for exploitation	Potential barriers
Short-term (0-4 years)	Data System - Define of data management system capable of providing novel data and securing sensitive ones. - Align data management to FAIR and open data principles, keeping dual technology in mind.	- Difficulties to provide accurate and robust data if scrubbing requires deleting important pieces – data management will be highly costly to keep this process ongoing. - Conflicting requirements between FAIR/open data principles and security/privacy concerns, especially with sensitive data.
	Infrastructure prototype - Design a data handling/storage prototype, standardised across Europe, that allows clear uptake for research/industrial uptake, while deleting more sensitive data.	- Complexities in ensuring seamless deletion of sensitive data without compromising system integrity or usability.
	Use cases - Increase scientific production that highlights the potential of analysis based on accurate fibre sensing data. - Identify key private stakeholders to enhance collaboration in terms of data accessing and sharing.	- Difficulty in generating significant interest from the academic community in a short time frame. Similar could be extended to private sector. - Lack of incentives for private stakeholders to share their data, especially if there's a competitive edge at stake.
Medium-term (5-9 years)	Governance model - Develop a governance and financial mechanism that works for data and infrastructure - Define a legal status for this governing body (e.g. ERIC) and leverage this for enhancing funding mechanisms.	- Risk of conflicting interests between stakeholders (academia, industry, government) that can delay decision-making. - Lengthy legal processes and bureaucracy to define legal status, especially for large-scale, multi-country infrastructures.
	Partnerships - Define cross-benefits and added value points for collaborations with private sector - Design/Integrate a community of practice of researchers working with this technology	- Misaligned goals between academic/research-focused stakeholders and profit-driven private sector actors.
	User engagement - Map and approach new user communities and develop ad-hoc engagement actions (also short term).	- Identifying and reaching relevant user communities can be time-consuming and resource-intensive.
Long-term (over 10 years)	ESFRI roadmap - Improve positioning of the infrastructure within the ESFRI landscape – this is a long-term vision strategy looking to create synergies with other actions (user engagement, funding, etc.)	- Difficulty in aligning the infrastructure's long-term goals with constantly evolving EU funding and innovation policies.
	Excellence in R&I - Promote and deepen excellence in research results and propose innovation to	- Potentially rapid technological change requiring upgrade and refining of approach.

Target timing	Actions for exploitation	Potential barriers
	the infrastructure and associated processes.	
	Societal benefits - Use research results to influence policymaking and address societal challenges - Leverage the capacity of the technology to improve funding streams.	- Difficulty in translating technical results into actionable policy recommendations - Limited political will or interest in adopting the research outcomes

6 Next steps

The upcoming phase of the **SUBMERSE** project will focus on refining the exploitation strategy through collective discussions and aligning the project's outcomes with European policy goals. This process will build on the insights gathered from initial consortium meetings and workshops, emphasising collaborative engagement and stakeholder input.

The next steps involve facilitating further discussions among project partners to fine-tune the exploitation pathways. These discussions will concentrate on identifying high-potential use cases, optimising data management strategies, and exploring new opportunities for cross-sector collaboration. A critical focus will be placed on engaging with both scientific and industrial stakeholders to ensure the project's technologies and datasets are effectively leveraged beyond the academic domain. The aim is to create a sustainable framework that supports the long-term use of the project's outputs and accelerates their adoption across different industries.

The final version of the sustainability and exploitation plan will include further analysis – not yet ready at this stage of the project – such as:

- Analysis of TRL level of technology and potential applications
- A list of key exploitation items, including owners and beneficiaries involved; Type of item (tool, training material, etc); Description; Sectors of applications; TRL status; and IP protection strategy.
- Detailed analysis of exploitation strategy by project partner, aligned with the proposed governance model.